

Studies on Some Telluro-vanado-tungstates

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Ammonium telluro-vanado-tungstate, $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{WO}_3 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been synthesised and its composition determined by analytical method. Its properties have been studied. Silver, barium, lead, and iron salts have been prepared from the ammonium salt. Differential thermal analysis of the ammonium salt has been carried out to investigate the thermal changes.

The role of tungsten and vanadium in the formation of heteropoly acids and their salts is well known and numerous condensation products in different ratios of $\text{WO}_3 \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ have been reported¹. Canneri² first reported the formation of tungsto-vanado-arsenate. Later³ he investigated various hetero-tri-acids and salts containing tungsten, vanadium, and phosphorus or arsenic. Boron has also been condensed to form hetero-triborotungsto-vanadic acid⁴.

The condensation reaction of telluric acid with tungstic acid was studied by Rosenheim and Traube⁵. Recently Ganelina⁶ prepared and studied telluric-12 tungstic heteropoly acid, $\text{H}_4 [\text{TeO}_4(\text{WO}_3)_{12}]$ and its silver salt⁷.

Formation of heteropoly salts of tellurium and vanadium has been studied in this laboratory⁸. The work has now been extended to investigate the hetero-tri-salt formation of telluric acid, vanadium pentoxide, and tungstic acid. The preparation and analysis of ammonium telluro-vanado-tungstate and its salts with silver, barium, lead, and iron are reported herein. The differential thermal analysis technique has been applied to study the thermal changes in the case of ammonium salt.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium Telluro-vanado-tungstate.—Telluric acid (4.6 g.) and vanadium pentoxide (7.3 g.) were refluxed in ammoniacal medium for 6 hr. and to it tungstic acid (20 g.), dissolved in sufficient ammonium hydroxide, was added and the mixture refluxed for another 10 hr. The solution was then evaporated to a small volume and kept in a refrigerator for crystalli-

1. *Annalen*, "Handbuch der anorganischen Chemie, 8 Auflage, Verlag Chemie G.M. B.H. Berlin 1923, p. 285.

2. *Gazzetta*, 1923, 53, 773.

3. *Ibid.*, 1926, 56, 642, 871.

4. Polotebnova, *Uchenye Zapiski, Kishinev, Gosudarst. Univ.*, 1957, 27, 83.

5. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1915, 81, 75.

6. *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1962, 7, 1570.

7. *Ibid.*, 1963, 8, 1891.

8. Prasad and Pathak, *this Journal*, 1966, 43, 176.

sation. The crystalline ammonium telluro-vanado-tungstate was obtained after two days and was recrystallised and analysed. [Found: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, 10.52; TeO_3 , 12.80; V_2O_5 , 25.99; WO_3 , 31.68; H_2O , 19.22. $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{WO}_3 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, 10.91; TeO_3 , 12.28; V_2O_5 , 25.47; WO_3 , 32.44; H_2O 18.99%].

Silver salt was prepared by adding dilute silver nitrate solution to the ammonium salt solution. It is a yellow compound, insoluble in water and ethanol. (Found: Ag_2O , 39.02; TeO_3 , 9.58; V_2O_5 , 20.82; WO_3 , 24.99; H_2O , 5.59. $3\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{WO}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag_2O , 38.51; TeO_3 , 9.72; V_2O_5 , 20.14; WO_3 , 25.65; H_2O , 5.98%).

Barium Salt.—When a dilute solution of barium chloride was added to the ammonium salt solution, a yellow compound began to separate. It was kept for a few hours to settle and then filtered, dried, and analysed. The compound is decomposed by acids. (Found: BaO , 28.53; TeO_3 , 11.34; V_2O_5 , 23.70; WO_3 , 28.52; H_2O , 7.91. $3\text{BaO} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{WO}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires BaO , 28.94; TeO_3 , 11.05; V_2O_5 , 22.01; WO_3 , 29.17; H_2O , 7.93%).

Lead Salt.—A heavy yellow precipitate was obtained by adding a solution of lead nitrate to ammonium salt solution. (Found: PbO , 38.18; TeO_3 , 9.96; V_2O_5 , 19.91; WO_3 , 25.12; H_2O , 6.83. $3\text{PbO} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{WO}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires PbO , 37.41; TeO_3 , 9.81; V_2O_5 , 20.33; WO_3 , 25.90; H_2O , 6.03%).

Iron Salt.—A freshly prepared dilute solution of ferric chloride formed a yellow precipitate when added to the ammonium salt solution. The compound is decomposed by acids. (Found: Fe_2O_3 , 12.82; TeO_3 , 13.03; V_2O_5 , 28.10; WO_3 , 34.90; H_2O , 11.15. $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{WO}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe_2O_3 , 12.22; TeO_3 , 13.44; V_2O_5 , 27.86; WO_3 , 35.48; H_2O , 11.05%).

Tellurium was estimated as metallic tellurium⁹ and ammonia, as described earlier¹⁰. Tungstic and vanadic acids were precipitated with HgNO_3 ; the moist precipitate was dissolved in HCl and the solution largely diluted. WO_3 was precipitated free from vanadium. The solution of vanadium was titrated against standard KMnO_4 at 70° in H_2SO_4 (dil.) medium. The water content was determined by difference as all the water molecules were not removed at 110° .

The apparatus employed in differential thermal analysis consists of an analytical furnace, a transformer, and recording equipment. Specimen holders were of alumina having the dimension $1'' \times 3/4'' \times 1/4''$. A heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min.}$ was employed with sample sizes ranging from 100 to 120 mesh. For D.T.A. studies, the salt was well mixed with extrapure alumina (E. Merck) and tightly packed in one cell, whereas alumina alone as reference material was taken in the other. The D.T.A. of ammonium salt was carried out.

DISCUSSION

On condensing telluric acid⁶ with tungstic acid and vanadium pentoxide⁸, the ammonium salt of the hetero-tri-acid was obtained. The composition of this acid has been desig-

9. Lenher and Homberger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 387.

10. Prasad and Pathak, *this Journal*, 1965, 42, 373.

nated on the basis of analytical results as it is difficult to assign definite structure owing to the large size of the molecule. The stability of the anion was confirmed by passing a freshly prepared solution of the ammonium salt through a cation-exchange resin (Amberlite IR-120); the tellurium, vanadium, and tungsten content of the solution remained unchanged. In precipitated silver, barium, lead, and iron salts, the anion conforms to the same composition in all the cases. The D.T.A. curve of the ammonium salt reveals two endotherms at about 105° and 250° (Fig. 1). Fig. 1 shows that the water molecules are removed in two stages, one at about 105° and the other at about 250°. Perhaps the water molecules (constitutional), which are closely packed in the interstices of the crystal lattice, are removed at a considerably higher temperature.

FIG. 1. Ammonium telluro-vanado-tungstate.

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